

Machine learning for compression of high energy physics data

Samuel Hill

10635164

School of Physics and Astronomy

The University of Manchester

MPhys project report

January 2024

This project was performed in collaboration with Malena Duroux.

Abstract

An analysis was carried out on the performance of Baler [1], a machine learning based data compression model, when compressing and reconstructing image data. The investigation focused on several factors that determine the applicability of Baler to high energy physics experiments. This involved the compression and reconstruction quality of images of different types of particle traversing a liquid argon chamber and the quality of real-time online image compression. Baler was found to perform high quality online compression on diffusion images from the ExaFEL X-ray free electron laser project [2]. The mean squared error of images from the LArIAT experiment [3] showed that reconstruction was improved by approximately two orders of magnitude for datasets containing only one particle type compared to those containing a mix of particles. Also, visualisations of the compressed LArIAT data were also produced to investigate the effect of clustering on image compression and reconstruction.

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Machine learning for data compression	3
2.1	Key concepts	3
2.1.1	Basic definitions	3
2.1.2	Loss functions	3
2.1.3	Model training	4
2.1.4	Modelling non-linearity: activation functions and neural networks	5
2.2	Autoencoders	6
2.3	Baler	6
3	Exafel dataset: online vs offline compression	7
3.1	Online vs offline compression	7
3.2	Input data	7
3.3	Results and discussion	7
4	LArIAT dataset: neutrino data compression and latent space visualisation	8
4.1	LArIAT experiment overview	8
4.2	Particle detection and imaging	9
4.3	Input data	11
4.3.1	Original data	11
4.3.2	Cleaning and splitting data	11
4.4	Latent space visualisation	12
4.4.1	Motivation	12
4.4.2	Dimensionality reduction	13
4.5	Results and discussion	13
4.5.1	Compression of LArIAT images	13
4.5.2	Latent space visualisation	15
5	Conclusions and outlook	18

1 Introduction

High energy physics is study of the most fundamental particles in our universe and their interactions. Large collaborations at facilities such as the European Organisation for Nuclear Research (CERN) perform experiments that search for events like proton-proton collisions that can provide evidence to test new theories. Searching for interesting events can often be like searching for a needle in a haystack so the more data that can be collected for these experiments the better. However, even these large collaborations have limits of how much data they can physically store so compression is very valuable for collecting as much data as possible. In order to preserve the physical significance of experimental data it is important to understand said data and tailor compression to suit it best. Machine learning is a very useful tool for automatically performing this tailoring and achieving a high quality compression. This report investigates the performance of a machine learning based compression model called Baler [1], developed at the University of Manchester and Lund University.

Due to the adaptability of machine learning based compression, we can perform compression on data from a variety of fields. Two main datasets are covered in this report: X-ray free electron laser data from the ExaFEL project [2] and neutrino data from the LArIAT experiment [3]. Two other test datasets, one from a computational fluid dynamics simulation and the other from the CMS collaboration at CERN, were used to initially understand how to run Baler and evaluate its performance but do not feature in this report. The ExaFEL dataset was used to investigate the quality of online compression, a means of compressing data continuously as it is collected. Then, the LArIAT dataset was used to test how well images of different particles in a neutrino detector compress and to visualise the data in its compressed form as a means of better understanding how Baler compresses input data. All topics of investigation in this report are relevant to problems faced by large scale high energy physics experiments and aim to provide insight for future applications in this context.

2 Machine learning for data compression

2.1 Key concepts

2.1.1 Basic definitions

Machine learning is very powerful for making predictions or classifying never-before-seen data by learning from example data given by the user. Understanding the data we use is one of the most important aspects of machine learning. In a given dataset we call each instance of data an example, for instance each image in a set of images. Each example consists of a number of variables called features and can also include a label. We can think of labels and features being equivalent to y and the set $\{x_i\}$ respectively, where y is some variable that varies as a function of $\{x_i\}$. There is however an important distinction; while the relationship between y and the $\{x_i\}$ is exactly defined by a function, features are just a set of useful pieces of information that we use to predict the value of the quantity that the label represents. For example, a model that wants to predict a person's height may use features such as weight, age and gender and has height as the label. Labels are the true value for an example, which can be compared to the value predicted by our model based on the input features. An example of input features from the Baler project is in image compression and reconstruction, where each pixel of the input image is its own feature, being the obvious information required in order to reconstruct that same image.

Input features can be combined together to produce a single output in an object called a neuron. Neurons are the building blocks of many machine learning models and can be joined together to form what is called a neural network, allowing for much more complex predictions than for a single neuron. A neuron establishes a linear relationship between an output y and its input features $\{x_i\}$, each with their own coefficients called weights, $\{w_i\}$ and biases, $\{b_i\}$

$$y = \sum_{i \in \text{Features}} b_i + w_i x_i. \quad (1)$$

These weights and biases may seem a bit abstract but they are key when training a neuron to give a more accurate output. However, to do this we firstly need something to quantify the quality of an output.

2.1.2 Loss functions

We use a loss function to quantify how badly a neuron makes predictions based on the input features and look to reduce this by an iterative process. A loss function can combine various terms relating to different negative aspects of a model that we wish to discourage. A very common term for a loss function is mean squared error (MSE), defined as

$$MSE = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(y_i - y'_i)^2}{N} \quad (2)$$

where the $\{y_i\}$ are the outputs of the neuron, the $\{y'_i\}$ are the known labels for each example and N is the number of examples in the dataset. Mean squared error uses the differences between label and output to quantify how poorly a neuron predicts or reconstructs data. Therefore, by minimising this error we improve the quality of prediction or reconstruction achieved by our model. Another common term in a loss function is L1 regularisation which takes the form

$$L1 = \sum_{i=1}^N |w_i|. \quad (3)$$

This term reflects the amount of features contributing to the neuron's output by summing the weights of the model. We care about this as sometimes there are uninformative features in our model that we can reject to save on computational input. This is called promoting model sparsity and is essentially reducing the size of our model. There is another form of loss term called L2 regularisation that quantifies the amount of complexity in a model. As well as combining different loss terms in our

overall loss function, we can multiply these terms by scalar parameters that can be modified by the user depending on how much they wish to focus on minimising a particular issue like reconstruction error or complexity. Parameters such as these that we modify manually according to our needs are called hyperparameters. While all computation is done automatically by our model, modifying hyperparameters to improve model performance is a large part of the how we as humans use machine learning effectively.

2.1.3 Model training

We train a model using an iterative technique for minimising the loss function called gradient descent. At each iteration, called an epoch, we compute the loss function before calculating its gradient with respect to each of the weights and biases individually. In practice, the calculation of these gradients is done automatically by inbuilt functions in machine learning frameworks such as PyTorch and TensorFlow. Once the gradient is calculated, we take a step in the direction of negative gradient, like moving down the valley of the loss function to find its lowest point as shown in Figure 1. If successful, by repeating this process we should converge on at least a local minimum of the loss function with respect to each weight and bias. The size of each step is called the learning rate and is another important hyperparameter for the efficacy of training. Optimising learning rate can require a Goldilocks-like approach. If too small, we may take too long to approach a local minimum as we approach it in small steps but if too large we may miss a local minimum as the large steps cause us to jump straight past it, meaning our model continues to jump around and never converges. Another choice for the user to make is how many examples to use when calculating gradients. The Baler model uses what is called batched learning, where we only use a batch of examples chosen randomly from the dataset for each gradient calculation. This provides a good representation of the whole dataset while still saving on computation.

Figure 1: Optimising learning rate, $f(w)$ represents the loss function [4].

The goal of machine learning is not just to model a single situation to give the most precise prediction of some dependent variable based on a set of other variables. Rather, it is for the model to learn patterns and relationships so that it can make accurate predictions on data it has never seen before. This underpins the concept of overfitting. If we train a model on a large set of examples, it may become very complex and learn exactly how to predict the values of those examples but lose its generality by taking into account small quirks of the data it has seen that do not appear in other similar datasets. As a result, this model would perform very poorly when shown another dataset with its own small quirks. This is why it is useful to use L2 regularisation to reduce complexity in a model. A good way to spot overfitting is to split our data into a test and training set.

We often split our dataset randomly into a large training set and a smaller test set in order to see if our model has learned general trends or overfit to the training data. If done properly, the value of the loss function for the test set should usually be only slightly greater than that of the training set, with a large difference often pointing to overfitting as the loss is much higher for data that the model hasn't seen during training. In general, it is useful to produce a plot of loss against the number of

epochs once your model has been trained. We normally hope to see the loss smoothly decrease as the model optimises weights and biases to best fit the data, before plateauing as the model converges on its optimum configuration. A lack of such a plateau may suggest you need to train your model for more epochs. Another essential thing to remember when splitting your data is not to cheat by training on your test data. If you do this, the model has already seen and learnt from the data in what is supposed to be a blind test of its generality, leading to a misleadingly low loss for the test data. To avoid this, we always split our data before doing anything else regarding training a machine learning model.

2.1.4 Modelling non-linearity: activation functions and neural networks

As mentioned before, a single neuron can only model a linear relationship between the inputs and an output. In reality this relationship will often be much more complex so we use objects called activation functions to directly introduce non-linearities. We take the weighted sum of the inputs produced by our neuron and pass it through the activation function. An activation function could in principle be any mathematical function, but there are several common ones that can be used out-of-the-box with PyTorch or TensorFlow. One common function is the sigmoid, of the form

$$F(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}, \quad (4)$$

which casts the weighted sum to a number between 0 and 1. Another is rectified linear unit activation (ReLU), of the form

$$F(x) = \max(0, x). \quad (5)$$

This casts the weighted sum to zero when negative and leaves it as it was it when positive. A variation of ReLU is called leaky ReLU; this allows a small positive gradient for a negative input rather than returning zero. This is helpful for avoiding the vanishing gradient problem [5], where the gradient of a node is cast to zero meaning the weight can no longer change its value via gradient descent and training may be interrupted.

While activation functions do introduce non-linearity, it is by stacking non-linearities on non-linearities that we achieve the level of model complexity required for most purposes in machine learning. This is done in a neural network, where layers of individual neurons, now referred to as nodes, are connected together with activation functions transforming the outputs of the nodes in each layer. In between the input and output we add sets of nodes called hidden layers, with each node a weighted sum of the nodes in the previous layer. A model is called fully connected if each node in a layer connects to every other node in its neighbouring layers. Figure 2 shows a simple example of this kind of structure and illustrates what happens in a given node of a neural network. The Σ on the left of the node represents the weighted sum of the activations from the previous layer. The f on the right of the node is the output of the activation function when given the weighted sum as an input. This is what is taken by the next layer when calculating the weighted sum for that layer. Each arrow in the figure has a weight and each node has a bias, both of which are varied to optimise the model. Each epoch of training consists of two stages: forward propagation and backward propagation. In forward propagation we pass layer by layer from the input to the output calculating the weighted sums and activations of each node and use the output to calculate the loss function. Then, during backward propagation we pass from output to input, modifying the weights and biases at each layer using gradient descent.

All description of the training process so far has been of what is called supervised learning. There also exists other types of training such as unsupervised learning, where we do not require each example to have an explicit label in order to perform training.

Figure 2: Example of a simple neural network [6].

2.2 Autoencoders

There are two main types of data compression, lossless and lossy, and choosing which to use comes down to the type of data we have and what our goals are for the compression [7]. Lossless compression reduces file size without losing any of its information. While this allows for perfect data reconstruction upon decompression, we can obviously only compress our data so much this way. Also, compression techniques are often tailored to a particular type of data and will not work for any arbitrary dataset. Lossy compression discards part of the input data and use approximations to reconstruct data, leading to a much larger potential for compression. When using data compression for scientific research it is important for us to assess how much the physical meaning of our data has been jeopardised. Autoencoders uses machine learning to tailor lossy compression to previously unseen input data.

Autoencoders are a special type of neural network that can be used to compress data by dimensionality reduction [8]. The aim is to reproduce the input in the output while using a bottleneck structure for compression. Autoencoders use a special type of learning called semi-supervised learning, as the model produces its own labels from the input rather than being given the data with an explicit label and set of examples. The structure consists of five consecutive sections called the input, encoder, code, decoder and output. The input and output have the same dimension, defined by the number of features. The input is then passed through the encoder which is a series of fully connected layers, the number of nodes decreasing with each layer as determined by the user. The output of the encoder, called the code, is our compressed data and is also referred to as the latent space representation. The size of the latent space is also defined by the user and the ratio of the size of the input and the size of the latent space is called the compression ratio, R . Obviously the greater our R value the greater the compression, but this may come at a cost in data fidelity when we decompress the data afterwards. Given that the model training is self-governed, the exact contents of the latent space can be somewhat of a black box. As such, visualising and trying to understand the latent space of the Baler model was one of the goals for this project. After compression, the code is then passed through the decoder to the output. The decoder is another series of fully connected layers this time increasing in size with each layer.

2.3 Baler

Baler is a published international collaboration that uses an autoencoder to tailor lossy compression. This works well for very large datasets such as in high energy physics (HEP) and has also been used in several other contexts such as computational fluid dynamics [1]. It is an open source project that is written in Python using the PyTorch machine learning framework. The model used and all hyperparameters can be specified by the user in a config file that is used to run the model. There are several models that are suited to different kinds of data. Here we will be using a model called CFD dense AE that was initially intended for use on computational fluid dynamics data. The model is called dense as all layers in the encoder and decoder are fully connected. The encoder and decoder are symmetric, with the encoder having three layers of 200, 100 and 50 nodes that use a leaky ReLU activation function. The loss function, L , is given by,

$$L = (1 - \beta)L_{reco} + \beta L_{sparse} \quad (6)$$

where L_{reco} is the MSE, L_{sparse} is the L1 regularisation and β is a free hyperparameter. This prioritises a good reconstruction and a sparse model in order to reduce the amount of data storage required not just for the files but for the saved model itself. Unless stated otherwise a compression ratio of 100 was used throughout this report.

Baler produces metrics for assessing the quality of reconstruction according to the type of input data. Two main metrics were used for the images studied in this report. One of these is a figure containing the original image, the reconstructed image and a third image showing the difference between the two. This shows qualitatively how well the model has performed overall but also can highlight particular regions in the image that are reconstructed well or poorly. We can make an order of magnitude estimate for the relative reconstruction error from these plots. The other metric is a plot showing the training loss at each epoch of training (closely related to the MSE by Equation 6 for small β), averaged over all images in the dataset. This is useful as it provides the average loss, and hence average reconstruction error, in one concise figure that can be used to compare between different datasets. However, it does not provide any information on how reconstruction quality varies for different images in the dataset. A potential improvement to the analysis in this report would be to include along with the loss plot a histogram of the losses for all the images in a dataset. This would be more useful than having to select example images to represent the whole dataset when the large number of images makes it inefficient to try to show visually the reconstruction quality of all the images.

3 Exafel dataset: online vs offline compression

This section has two main goals: to test the quality of compression on data from the ExaFEL project and to use this data to test the efficacy of Baler when performing online compression (a way of performing compression in real time).

3.1 Online vs offline compression

An autoencoder can use what is called offline or online compression [1]. Offline compression is when a model is trained on a dataset then only used to compress that same dataset. Whereas, online compression refers to training a model on one dataset then continuing to use that same model on other datasets without retraining on each new dataset. Online compression allows us to compress data as we produce it using a pre-trained model so it can be stored more efficiently. This is very useful in large HEP experiments where vast amounts of data are produced continuously only for most of it to be thrown away.

Baler so far has only been used to test offline compression. To test online compression we need two datasets from the same experiment as in practice a model used to continuously compress data coming in from an experiment would also be trained on data from that experiment. This is the case with the datasets used in this section.

3.2 Input data

The ExaFEL project takes data from an X-ray Free Electron Laser that uses diffraction to image atoms and molecules [2]. The project aims at reducing the data analysis timescale to allow for near real-time interpretation. This is important given the limited beam time available to experiments using free electron lasers. The data used in this experiment is a series of images that form an animation of X-ray radiation diffracting around an individual atom. Two datasets of the same experiment were used, named ExaFEL 1 and ExaFEL 2.

3.3 Results and discussion

The CFD dense AE model was trained and used to perform compression and decompression on both ExaFEL datasets. Each was then compressed and decompressed using the model from the other

dataset. Figure 3 shows three example difference plots for offline and online compression of the ExaFEL 2 dataset.

Figure 3: Examples plots for the ExaFEL 2 dataset of original image, reconstructed image and the difference between the two. The same images are treated using offline compression (a) and online compression (b).

The difference plots show near perfect reconstruction for both online and offline compression. A loss plot could not be produced to give a more quantitative measure of performance for online compression as no training was performed. However, simply calculating the mean squared error for each image would be a useful next step to try to quantify this.

4 LArIAT dataset: neutrino data compression and latent space visualisation

4.1 LArIAT experiment overview

The Liquid Argon in a Testbeam (LArIAT) experiment [3] tracks particles by taking spatial and calorimetric measurements of the particle in its detector. It is one of many Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers (LArTPC), a very popular type of experiment in neutrino physics. Another example of these detectors is the Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE) [9], which is set to be the flagship neutrino experiment in the US once completed. We hope that the results of testing compression on data from a smaller experiment like LArIAT can then be extrapolated to these other larger experiments where the vast amount of data collected will make data compression very valuable. We had two main goals for this section of the project. The first was to investigate and compare the quality of data reconstruction after compression for different types of particle used in LArIAT. The second was to visualise the latent space of the autoencoder used for compression and use this to better understand how the model works (this will be explained in more depth in a later subsection).

LArTPCs are designed to track charged particles produced as a result of neutrino-nucleus interactions. They produce 2D spatial projection images of the particle paths in a volume of liquid argon. It is the behaviour of the charged particles that we use to infer information about the neutrinos, such as investigating neutrino oscillations, which is the real scientific goal of most experiments using LArTPCs [10]. However, studying these charged particles interactions when the particles result from neutrino-nucleus interactions adds extra uncertainty related to the nature of the neutrino interactions themselves, thus muddying the characterisation of the charged particles. The LArIAT experiment

attempts to resolve this by producing charged particles in a testbeam of the same type and energies as those produced in neutrino-nucleus reactions. Producing these particles of known type and momentum in a controlled environment allows particle identification and reconstruction methods to be refined which can then be used in other LArTPCs.

4.2 Particle detection and imaging

The time projection chamber (TPC) is where imaging of the charged particles takes place. It is a homogenous chamber of liquid argon with dimensions 47cm x 40cm x 90cm. The TPC is flanked on either side by a cathode and an anode, creating a uniform electric field perpendicular to the incoming particle beam in a similar way to a parallel plate capacitor. The cathode provides a negative high voltage while the anode is positively charged and made up of two planes of parallel, equidistant wires.

In the TPC there are two processes used to track the energy and trajectory of a charged particle coming from the testbeam. The first of these is the production of so-called drift electrons due to the charged particle ionising argon atoms as it propagates through the TPC. These electrons form a sort of shadow along the trajectory of the particle, like the water vapour trail left by a plane. We call them drift electrons as they drift collectively towards the wire planes, parallel to the uniform electric field and maintaining the form of the particle trajectory as they do so (ignoring small effects like diffusion). Drift velocity for these electrons is easily calculable using the known electric field. Typical drift time from initial ionisation site to the wire planes for electrons is of the order of tens of milliseconds. The second process is the production of scintillation light from argon atoms. This occurs when the charged particle excites electrons in the argon atom into a higher energy state, leading to the emission of a photon as the electrons subsequently deexcite. Scintillation light is detected almost instantaneously by photodetectors just beyond the wire planes. Because of this we can take the time when scintillation light is first detected from a particular point to be when a charged particle is at said point interacting with the argon.

Drift electrons are detected in two wire planes, called the induction and collection planes, located on the side of the TPC. Figure 4 shows the TPC with the wires oriented at $\pm 60^\circ$ with respect to the z axis. When a drift electron reaches one of the wires it deposits charge, producing an electrical signal. The total signal read out from the wire in a given time interval is proportional to the total charge deposited in the wire and hence the number of electrons that touch that wire. The wires are separated by a 3mm gap and numbered so we know which wire an electron drifts to and therefore get information about its position.

The images produced are a 2D spatial projection of the charged particle trajectory with the amplitude of the signal showing deposited ionisation charge. On the horizontal axis is wire number which is proportional to distance in the direction lying in the wire plane and perpendicular to the wires. As the wires are all equally spaced, the actual distance in this direction is simply wire number multiplied by the wire gap. The vertical axis is drift time which is the time elapsed between detection of scintillation light and the electron reaching the wire. This is proportional to distance in the direction of increasing drift time as labelled in Figure 4, the actual distance being drift time multiplied by the drift velocity. There are two wire planes therefore each event produces two images, capturing a projection of the particle trajectory from different angles.

Images can be distinguished by different particle types, as each has their own characteristic tracks determined by how they interact with the argon in the TPC. One example is electromagnetic showers (referred to also as electron-like showers) that are characteristic of high-energy electrons, positrons and photons. These showers are also observed with the π^0 as it decays into two photons, leading to two separate showers. The primary interactions of photons in matter are dependent on their energy. One of these interactions is pair production, where a photon is converted into an electron-positron pair that travel away in different directions to conserve momentum. This is one of two key processes involved in producing showers and can only occur at energies over roughly 1 MeV as the photon's energy must exceed twice the rest mass of an electron for them to be produced. The other key process is called bremsstrahlung, where an electron is decelerated when deflected by a positively charged argon nucleus

and a photon is produced carrying energy away. The repetitive process in which an electron produces a photon by bremsstrahlung which then creates an electron-positron pair which each produce photons and so on is what forms the cascade of particles. An example of one of these showers is shown in Figure 5. As the electron's kinetic energy is lost at each step of this process during bremsstrahlung, particle energy decreases along the cascade until it drops below the threshold for pair production. At this point the shower stops and photons interact via the photoelectric effect or Compton scattering.

Figure 4: Schematic diagram showing the setup of the time projection chamber in the LArIAT experiment [3] and process for particle detection (above). Also shown are example images for ionisation electrons collected in the induction and collection planes (below).

Figure 5: Schematic illustration of an electromagnetic shower initiated by a photon [11].

4.3 Input data

4.3.1 Original data

The data used in this report comes from a Monte Carlo simulation of the LArIAT experiment. LArIAT data is stored using a framework called artROOT [12] that is not compatible for use with Baler. However, we were able to use a dataset that had already been converted from the original format into numpy arrays which can be run in Baler. This conversion came with several artefacts. Firstly, the dataset only contains the collection plane image for each event, half of what is originally produced in the simulation. Also, the time axis is averaged over every 21 of the original time ticks, thus losing some resolution on the time axis. Finally, the axes are reversed compared to convention so the time axis is horizontal and the wire axis vertical. This however should have no effect on any physics analysis as all images are rotated by the same angle and the processes involved are invariant under spatial rotation.

The dataset contains 15000 images, each of a different event. These images were labelled according to the type of particle in the image. The fifteen labels, each with 1000 images, are: electrons_minus, electrons_plus, kaonminus, kaonplus_1, michel, michel_minus, muons_minus, photons, photons_minus, photons_plus, piminus, piminus_1, piplus_1, pizero and positrons_plus. The labels are mostly clear while others such as piminus and piminus_1 are taken to represent the same particles physically despite slight differences in label. The labels michel and michel_minus refer to Michel electrons, a special type of electron produced when a muon decays at rest. To check which particle is described by each label, we looked at the first 5 images for each label to see if the tracks looked consistent with how we would expect them to for that particle.

4.3.2 Cleaning and splitting data

Some data cleaning was performed on the raw dataset before splitting it up into smaller datasets to suit our needs. Nearly 2500 of the images contain almost only background noise. This is because there is a small region of liquid argon the particles need to traverse before reaching the imaging region. Some particles like pions and kaons are prone to undergoing other processes like decay that prevent them from reaching the imaging region but the image is still produced as the simulation automatically produces an image for each particle fired in the testbeam. In Figure 6, we plotted the sum of the numpy array corresponding to each image, which we referred to loosely as the total charge, as a way of identifying the empty images. From this we defined a total charge of 400 as the cut-off point for background noise and created a new label for all images below this point called noise. Figure 6 shows that pions, kaons and photons produced the majority of empty images. The noise cut-off left 12640 events not counting the noise images.

The dataset was split into one randomly mixed dataset and several split-by-particle datasets. The randomly mixed dataset contained 250 events for each of the ten types of particle: electron, positron, K^- , K^+ , Michel electron, muon, photon, π^- , π^+ and π^0 . A list of labels for the shuffled images was created as it would be useful later for latent space visualisation. All the images not used in the random dataset were then put into datasets containing only that type of particle. Splitting the data this way allowed us to compare and assess the reconstruction of different particles on their own and in a mix of other particles.

An artificial dataset was also made using a single event image by rotating it progressively by increments of 1° , giving a set of 360 rotated images of the same event. The images can be classified into two categories: images containing a particle track and empty images containing only background noise. This is because the original image has a rectangular aspect ratio and in order for Baler to train on the whole dataset all images must keep this same aspect ratio. Consequently, as the image was rotated there were some small ranges of rotation angle where the particle track was rotated out of the frame, leaving only background noise. The dataset was initially made as a way of testing Baler on LArIAT data before the whole 15000 event dataset was ready for use but proved to be a useful test of how the model handles data that has been rotated. This is important as the particle tracks in our LArIAT dataset are not all at the same angle so the model should be able to learn about different particle tracks regardless of their orientation.

Figure 6: A plot of the total charge for each image in the LArIAT dataset. Images are colour coded by particle and a log scale is used on the y axis for easier viewing of the images with low total charge.

4.4 Latent space visualisation

4.4.1 Motivation

The latent space represents our compressed data. It is not straightforward to understand exactly why it takes the form that it does but doing so can help to understand how an autoencoder works. The LArIAT dataset is suited to visualisation as it is labelled (this will become clear later).

LArIAT images have a dimensionality of 240 (pixels) by 146 (pixels) = 35040 as it takes 35040 values to define an image. In an autoencoder the dimensionality of the input is reduced by a factor equal to the compression ratio as it passes through the encoder to the latent space. During compression, the model has to essentially summarise the key distinguishing features of an input image and use these to represent the image as the latent space is too small to represent it in its original form. As a result, similar images that may differ subtly but have the same key features are cast to similar regions in the latent space, as only these common features survive the compression and are used to represent the compressed image. This congregation of similar images is called clustering. A common dataset that demonstrates clustering is the openly available MNIST labelled set of images of handwritten digits [13]. This dataset is used ubiquitously to test image processing. Each digit from 0 to 9 has its own characteristic features, for example a 7 has a horizontal line connected to a diagonal line. Because each image is labelled by digit, it is easy to see where different digits are cast in the latent space and how they cluster. In the LArIAT dataset, certain types of particles leave tracks with distinguishable characteristics so we may expect them also to cluster. For example, electrons-like particle showers are distinct from other straight line tracks and could theoretically be recognised by the model. It should be noted that the primary goal of an autoencoder is not to classify images in the latent space. Despite this, when passing the latent space representation through the decoder to produce the output, this clustering may aid reconstruction by providing expected characteristics for an image within that cluster.

Clustering can however lead to the issue of overclassifying in the latent space, where an image is reconstructed as how the model predicts an example of that type should look rather than being loyal to the original image. For example, an abnormal looking 1 in the MNIST dataset could be reconstructed as a typical looking 1 rather than reconstructing the original image. Visualising the latent space of our compressed LArIAT data could help to understand if clustering plays a role in image reconstruction.

4.4.2 Dimensionality reduction

As previously mentioned, the encoder reduces the dimensionality of our input data e.g. to a latent space of size 351 using a compression ratio of 100. However it is still almost impossible for us to visualise data in more than three dimensions. Therefore another technique is required to reduce the dimensionality of the latent space for visualisation while trying to preserve the structure of our data. There are several dimensionality reduction techniques; in this report we will focus on two of these.

The first technique is called t-distributed stochastic neighbour embedding (t-SNE) [14]. This technique focuses on local structure of the original higher dimensional data and looks to preserve the relationships between individual data points. For each data point, t-SNE allocates neighbouring points and uses a stochastic process to place these points in the lower dimensional representation such that they have the same amount of neighbours. In practice, t-SNE often produces very clear clusters somewhat artificially as a result of its dimensionality reduction.

The second dimensionality reduction technique is called TriMap and was pioneered by a Google research team [15]. Rather than focusing on local behaviour, TriMap focuses on global behaviour and tries to conserve the relative placement of clusters. TriMap is more suited to our goals as we wish to preserve the global structure of the latent space produced by Baler rather than producing further clustering as may be the case for t-SNE. In all our analysis of clusters however there is still an element of uncertainty regarding how true the two dimensional representation of our data produced by TriMap is to the Baler latent space.

4.5 Results and discussion

4.5.1 Compression of LArIAT images

The first images to be compressed were those from the artificial rotated dataset. Example reconstructions of images containing a particle track and those containing only noise are shown in Figure 7. The images with a particle track showed a near perfect reconstruction with a faint ring of reconstructed signal around a circle formed by rotating the original track through the full 360° . This is because although the model can confidently predict where to reconstruct the particle track it still weakly reconstructs the track in all locations where the track was at some point during the full rotation.

Figure 7: Examples reconstructions for the rotated LArIAT dataset of an image containing a particle track (above) and one containing only background noise (below). A faint ring is barely visible in the above reconstructed image.

The empty images exhibit a poor reconstruction, suggesting that the model hasn't focused much on the background noise. For the purpose of analysing the charged particles this is not too concerning but there are some physical questions surrounding the noise for which it would be important to preserve background noise after compression.

Baler was then run on the dataset containing a random mix of particles. The learning rate was first set to 0.001, then increased to 0.005 as an attempt to help the model converge faster, each time being run for 1000 epochs. A loss of about 10^3 for compression with learning rate 0.005 is seen in Figure 8a. Figure 8b shows typical reconstructions for the mixed dataset. An example of an electron-like shower, which typically presented a better reconstruction, is shown in the top row while an example for the other images in the dataset is shown in the bottom row. Similarly to the faint ring in the reconstruction of the rotated images, there is a weak background reconstruction resembling a collection of the similar showers from the whole set of images. This suggests that the autoencoder is classifying the dataset and can identify the images that have an electron-like shower. It then slightly overclassifies, reconstructing these images based on the set of showers it has trained on and hence draws weakly from the other particle showers as well as the one belonging to that image.

Figure 8: The mixed LArIAT dataset compressed using Baler with learning rate 0.005. This figure contains the loss plot (a) and example reconstructions (b). Typical reconstruction for non shower images are on the top row and shower images on the bottom row.

One proposed way of improving performance was to introduce 250 empty event images into the mixed dataset, the hope being that the model would better learn the background noise for reconstruction. This resulted in a slight improvement in model performance as the loss dropped just below 10^3 .

Baler was also used to compress the split-by-particle datasets. Reconstruction quality was significantly improved for these datasets compared to the mixed dataset. This is not surprising as the model only has to learn from images with broadly similar tracks as opposed to a wider range for the mixed set. Figure 9 shows loss plots and reconstructions for positrons and π^+ particles as examples of reconstruction quality.

The losses of order 10 and 100 for π^+ particles and positrons respectively are both significant improvements on that of the mixed dataset. All split-by-particle datasets had losses of order 10 to 100.

Whether looking at the mixed dataset or the split-by-particle datasets it is clear that reconstruction could still be improved. This is not unexpected as the largest of these, the mixed dataset, only contains 2500 images. For comparison, the MNIST dataset contains 60,000 images. This relatively

Figure 9: Example loss plots and reconstructions for the split-by-particle datasets: π^+ (a) and positrons (b).

small number of images means that the autoencoder simply doesn't have as much available training data from which to learn. One possible solution to this would be to create rotated versions of the mixed and split-by-particle datasets where for each image we create artificial rotations as with our rotated dataset. This would increase the number of images by a factor of 360 and would let the model train on particle tracks at all possible orientations. As a result, the model may focus less on the path orientation which is mainly determined by the incident direction of the beam and instead focus on characteristic features of the particle track itself.

4.5.2 Latent space visualisation

Before looking at the latent space of the LArIAT data, Baler was used to compress the MNIST dataset. MNIST images are 28×28 so a compression ratio of 392 was used to reduce the Baler latent space dimension to 2, allowing for visual comparison with t-SNE and TriMap to assess the relative extent of clustering. The model was trained for 2000 epochs, allowing more time to converge given the increase in compression. Figure 10 shows the loss plot for this training and example reconstructions of three MNIST images. The top row shows an example of misclassification, where the model has reconstructed a 4 as a 9. The bottom row exhibits overclassification as the original five with a distinct curvy tail is replaced by a more rounded, standard looking five. These both demonstrate issues associated with clustering when using Baler. On the other hand, the middle row shows a reasonably good reconstruction. The loss plot shows that the model has indeed converged to its optimal parameters.

The 2D Baler latent space is plotted alongside the MNIST data after dimensionality reduction using t-SNE and TriMap in Figure 11. We can see as expected that t-SNE creates more clearly defined clusters than TriMap. Baler produces less clustering than either TriMap or t-SNE but there is still some clear grouping of different digits with overlaps between some groups. The zeros have separated out the most while the nines and fours overlap heavily. This is consistent with the misclassification of a four as a nine in Figure 10. It should be noted that Baler is likely clustering more here than it would when normally used at lower compression ratios but given that we cannot visualise these higher dimensional latent spaces this cannot be shown.

Figure 10: MNIST dataset compressed to 2D using Baler: loss plot (a) and reconstruction images (b).

Figure 11: Comparison of dimensionality reduction techniques on MNIST dataset: t-SNE (a), TriMap (b), Baler (c). The plots for t-SNE and TriMap are taken from [15].

Finally, the mixed LArIAT dataset was compressed to a code size of 64 before reducing the latent space to two dimensions using TriMap. Colour coding was used to separate different particle types in the reduced latent space. Figure 12a shows the latent space with all different particle types while the other subfigures focus on the distribution of individual types of particle. Figure 12b shows the distribution of K^- particles, an example of particles showing no clustering. Figures 12c, 12d, 12e and 12f show clustering for photons, electrons, positrons and muons respectively. All particle types not shown in Figure 12 showed little to no clustering like for K^- . This is not surprising as the pions, kaons and Michel electrons do not have as distinctive characteristics as with electron showers. However, it is surprising that electrons and positrons seem to cluster better despite there not being a significant difference in the form of the showers they form. Also, electrons and positrons both cluster but in different regions of the reduced latent space when we would expect them to overlap given the theoretically identical showers they produce. This is possibly an artefact of how the electron images were produced as the electron images contained a thin strip of weakly negative signal at the boundaries

of the image. Muons cluster more than any of the other particles. This is an interesting but unexpected result that requires more investigation to be explained.

Figure 12: The latent space of the mixed LArIAT dataset reduced to two dimensions using TriMap. The plots show the distribution of: all particles (a), K^- (b), photons (c), electrons (d), positrons (e) and muons (f)

We have identified which particles are more prone to clustering by Baler and therefore present more unwanted low-level background reconstruction due to overclassification, which could potentially help us to fix this issue. However, those particles that don't suffer from overclassification still exhibit poor reconstruction, sometimes worse than those that do cluster. This remains an outstanding issue if this type of compression is to be used for detailed physics analysis.

5 Conclusions and outlook

Several conclusions have been made about the appropriateness of Baler for data compression in high energy physics. Using the ExaFEL dataset, online compression was found to perform just as well as offline compression. If this is found also to be true for high energy physics data then it could be very powerful as a means of compressing large amounts of data as it is produced so it does not need to be stored in its uncompressed form. The LArIAT dataset provided insight on the quality of compression and reconstruction for neutrino data. Reconstruction for a mix of particle types was generally found to be quite poor, with a mean squared error of around 10^3 . However, the quality of reconstruction was improved when working only with images of the same particle, yielding a mean squared error of order 10 to 100. Furthermore, it was found that particles that produce electromagnetic showers were more prone to clustering in the latent space, leading to overclassification and weak background reconstruction that is not present in the original images.

The performance metrics used in this report are a potential area for further improvement on the results found. The visual comparison using original and reconstructed images is useful for qualitatively assessing model performance and the loss plots allowed order of magnitude comparison of mean squared error averaged over the whole dataset. The latter was sufficient when comparing the losses of the split-by-particle and mixed LArIAT datasets but the exact mean squared errors would provide a more precise comparison. Also, a histogram of the mean squared error of all images would show the distribution of reconstruction quality across a dataset.

Other avenues of further investigation could include artificially increasing the size of the LArIAT dataset or trying models other than a dense autoencoder, both with the goal of improving reconstruction performance. In addition, compressing LArIAT data using conventional techniques like jpeg and comparing the results to compression with an autoencoder would be useful to assess the appropriateness of using autoencoders for data compression in high energy physics.

References

- [1] F. Bengtsson, C. Doglioni, P.A. Ekman, A. Gallén, P. Jawahar, A. Orucevic-Alagic et al., *Baler-machine learning based compression of scientific data*, *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.02283* (2023) .
- [2] A. Perazzo, *Exafel*, Feb, 2021.
- [3] R. Acciarri, C. Adams, J. Asaadi, M. Backfish, W. Badgett, B. Baller et al., *The liquid argon in a testbeam (lariat) experiment*, *Journal of Instrumentation* **15** (2020) P04026.
- [4] S. Kansal, *Quick guide to gradient descent and it's variants*, Aug, 2020.
- [5] S. Mastromichalakis, *Alrelu: A different approach on leaky relu activation function to improve neural networks performance*, *arXiv preprint arXiv:2012.07564* (2020) .
- [6] K. Melcher, *A friendly introduction to [deep] neural networks*, Aug, 2021.
- [7] K. Sayood, *Introduction to Data Compression*, Morgan Kaufmann series in multimedia information and systems, Morgan Kaufmann Publishers (1996).
- [8] T. Liu, J. Wang, Q. Liu, S. Alibhai, T. Lu and X. He, *High-ratio lossy compression: Exploring the autoencoder to compress scientific data*, *IEEE Transactions on Big Data* **9** (2023) 22.
- [9] DUNE collaboration, *Long-Baseline Neutrino Facility (LBNF) and Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE): Conceptual Design Report, Volume 2: The Physics Program for DUNE at LBNF*, [1512.06148](#).
- [10] D. Caratelli, W. Foreman, A. Friedland, S. Gardiner, I. Gil-Botella, G. Karagiorgi et al., *Low-energy physics in neutrino lartpcs*, *arXiv preprint arXiv:2203.00740* (2022) .
- [11] F. Si-liang, F. Peng, H. Yi-fan, M. Tian-yu and X. Yan, *The review of -ray astronomical observing techniques*, *Chinese Astronomy and Astrophysics* **45** (2021) 281.
- [12] R. Brun and F. Rademakers, *Root - an object oriented data analysis framework*, in *AIHENP'96 Workshop, Lausanne*, vol. 389, pp. 81–86, 1996.
- [13] L. Deng, *The mnist database of handwritten digit images for machine learning research*, *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine* **29** (2012) 141.
- [14] L. van der Maaten and G. Hinton, *Visualizing data using t-sne*, *Journal of Machine Learning Research* **9** (2008) 2579.
- [15] E. Amid and M.K. Warmuth, *Trimap: Large-scale dimensionality reduction using triplets*, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1910.00204* (2019) .
- [16] J. Nabi, *Machine learning -fundamentals*, May, 2019.
- [17] E. Tiu, *Understanding latent space in machine learning*, Feb, 2020.

References [16] and [17] are of further reading that is not cited in the text.

A special thanks is owed to my supervisors Prof Caterina Doglioni and Dr Elena Gramellini as well as Maria Gabriela Manuel Alves of the University of Campinas who provided the converted LArIAT data used in this report.